

Religion and Politics in the Eastern Vākāṭaka Kingdom

HANS BAKKER

The fourth and fifth centuries of the Christian era are often seen as the classical period of the cultural history of India. During this period India between the Himālaya and Vindhya mountains was united in the kingdom of the Guptas, whereas the northern part of the Deccan, south of the Vindhyas, which today forms the state of Maharashtra, was ruled by Vākāṭaka kings. As the major powers of their times, these two kingdoms, the northern and the southern, Gupta and Vākāṭaka, though formally independent, were connected through continuous exchange, ranging from military to matrimonial, from political ideology to culture, from religion to merchandise. The aims of this article are (1) to take a closer look at the historical process that threaded both kingdoms together and occasioned the rise of the dynasty of the Eastern Vākāṭakas, (2) to focus on how the Vākāṭaka rulers of the first half of the 5th century translated their sovereignty into monumental art, especially at the site of Mansar, and (3) to sketch how the culture of the eastern Vākāṭaka kingdom lost its momentum.

The Rise of the Eastern Vākāṭaka Dynasty

The second quarter of the 4th century A.D. had seen two power blocks beginning to emerge in northern India, both consolidated by strategic matrimonial alliances (see genealogy in Appendix I). In the Gangetic Plain Samudragupta had ascended to the throne, inheriting Candragupta I's kingdom as well as the territories of the Licchavis, a patrimony to which he was entitled through his mother, Kumāradevī. To the south of the northern plains the Vākāṭaka king Rudrasena I inherited at least parts of the kingdom of his grandfather, Pravarasena I, as well as the territories of the Bhāraśivas, a branch of the Nāga dynasty that ruled from Padmāvati, modern Pawayā. Rudrasena's father, Gautamīputra, had died before he could ascend the throne; his mother was a daughter of king Bhavanāga of the Bhāraśiva lineage, who was, it would seem, without male offspring, which made Rudrasena, like Samudragupta, a "daughter's son heir" (*dauhitra*).¹

A war in the sixth decade of the 4th century between these two power blocks resulted in a defeat

of the Nāga-Vākāṭaka alliance at the hands of Samudragupta. The Nāga were reduced to subordinate status in Vidiśā and Padmāvati; the Vākāṭakas, or at least one branch of the family, were forced to give up their homeland, which, as has been argued by A.M. Shastri, was possibly located in the Vindhyas (Vatsa, i.e. Bundelkhand).² They founded a new kingdom in Vidarbha, in the fertile Wainganga Plain south of the Satpura Range. Nandivardhana became the residence of these kings. Samudragupta's son, Candragupta II, concluded the peace with the old enemy by giving his daughter in marriage to Rudrasena II, the grandson of Rudrasena I, his father's former adversary. This princess, known from her charters as Prabhāvati Gupta, is one of the most remarkable women of classical India.

An inscription found in the Kevala-Narasimha Temple on Rāmagiri, Ramtek Hill, a steep hill c. 5 km north of the residence at Nandivardhan, reveals the dramatic history of Prabhāvati's mother, Kuberanāgā, the Nāga queen of Candragupta II. In describing the Gupta lineage the inscription suggests that the power (*śakti*) of the Nāgas had been curbed (*pratiśiddha*) to such an extent that one of their young princesses, who "had grown up like a flame", could be withdrawn from her father's authority (*pitur gṛhīta*) in order to be brought up at the Gupta court.³ This princess, Kuberanāgā, was subsequently, probably with a view to pacifying the Nāgas, given in marriage to Samudragupta's son Candragupta II as one of his chief wives (*mahādevī*).

The history of Prabhāvati's mother, born in the Nāga House, but grown up at the Gupta court, may have induced Prabhāvati to style herself, in her own inscriptions, explicitly as 'princess of the Nāga as well as Gupta family'. It seems even likely that her *gotra*, 'Dhāraṇa', was that of the Nāga family and not, as is usually assumed on the basis of later practice, that of her paternal lineage, the Guptas.⁴ The name Dhāraṇa occurs in the *Mahābhārata* list of Nāgas, said to be the sons of Kaśyapa (MBh 5.101.16). Prabhāvati's own inscriptions prove in any case that it was possible for princesses of high birth to retain their own *gotra* after being married.⁵ The *gotra* of the Guptas, if any, is unknown, since it is never mentioned in their own inscriptions. We may ask with Trautmann (1972, p. 15, n. 31):

1. Façade of Cave 12 Udayagiri.

Was Prabhāvatī's maternal line related to Bhavanāga [the great-great-grandfather of her husband]? The law of prohibited degrees which neither the Guptas nor the Vākātakas are otherwise known to have violated probably rules out too close a relationship, but it is tempting to see in Prabhāvatī's Nāga connexion the renewal of an old alliance between the Vākātakas and the Nāgas, as well as the start of a new one with the Guptas.

As we will see, the rules referred to were at least once violated and Trautmann's suggestion of a close relationship with the lineage of Bhavanāga has therefore become more feasible. The wedding between Candragupta's daughter Prabhāvatī and the Vākāṭaka prince Rudrasena must have taken place in the ninth decade of the 4th century.⁶ The princess brought with her the Vaiṣṇava Bhāgavata faith and the cultural assets and sophistication of the Gupta court. To judge by her inscriptions, in which seven lines are devoted to the eulogy of her imperial origins and only one line to her Vākāṭaka husband – denoting her father Candragupta as Mahārājādhirāja, her husband as Mahārājā – she might have thought herself far above the family of her in-laws, though her marriage was actually, in Dharmasāstra categories, *anuloma*.⁷

A tragic event meant that the Gupta princess had

to assume full responsibility for the royal house in which she had married. After a rule of less than a decade her husband died in c. A.D. 405, leaving her in her early thirties with three boys and at least one daughter. She acted as regent for her eldest son, the *yuvārāja* Divākarasena, for at least thirteen years as is shown by the Poona Plates of Prabhāvatī-guptā.⁸

However, the crown-prince died before he was allowed to ascend the throne. Prabhāvatī's regency over her two remaining sons may have lasted one or two years more, which brought the total duration of the rule of this dowager queen to thirteen or fourteen years, from c. A.D. 405 to 419, an exceptionally long term by Indian standards.⁹ If she had not had the full backing of the powerful Gupta family, it seems unlikely that her regency would have lasted so long. The conclusion is evident: Prabhāvatī more than just a regent, was virtually wearing the royal crown of the Vākāṭakas, no doubt to the satisfaction of her Gupta relatives.¹⁰

Evidence of the afore-mentioned Kevala-Narasimha Temple Inscription supports our inference that the power of Prabhāvatī Guptā was based on her alliance with the Guptas. In order to consolidate this relation she had her daughter, whose name is partly illegible but may have been Atibhāvatī (vs. 24), married

off to her half-brother, Ghaṭotkaca Gupta,¹¹ who ruled as a viceroy in Vidiśā over eastern Malwa and Bundelkhand at the time her other brother, Kumāragupta, held the imperial office.¹² The most probable date of this wedding is between Candragupta II's death (A.D. 415) and Pravarasena's accession to the throne (A.D. 419/422 ?). The former as well as the latter may have objected to Prabhāvati's extraordinary policy of taking advantage of her three-cornered relationship connecting her with the Guptas, Vākāṭakas and the Nāgas, over whose lands Ghaṭotkaca may have reigned as Gupta viceroy.¹³ Atibhāvati, referred to as his niece (*bhāgineyī*), may have been about sixteen years old at the time of her wedding to her maternal uncle. This princess, to whom the Ramtek Inscription may be ascribed, boasted of her Gupta affiliation rather than of her Vākāṭaka one. Just as in the inscriptions of her mother, the Gupta dynasty is eulogized extensively at the expense of Atibhāvati's Vākāṭaka relatives. It may be objected that this type of maternal uncle – niece marriage would be against the law (*dharma*), but so is the rule of a dowager, and it is a fact of life, in India as well as elsewhere, that power politics remains within the precincts of the law only as long as suits its aims. The present case corroborates an observation made by the foremost scholar of Dharmaśāstra, P. V. Kane, to the effect that "a very striking instance of the limits of *sapinda* relationship not being observed is the practice among certain sections of even brāhmaṇas... marrying their own sister's daughter."¹⁴ It thus seems that we are here concerned with an unprecedented example of matrimonial policy to consolidate matrilinear bonds. Whether everyone in the Vākāṭaka family was happy at the wedding is another matter. As will be shown below, the girl's brother undertook serious steps to annul this matrimonial alliance after her husband's death.

It thus appears that Prabhāvati Guptā, though residing in Nandivardhana in the Northern Deccan, was very well acquainted with the situation in Daśārṇadeśa, i.e. eastern Malwa. She might have visited Vidiśā as a young girl to see her mother's relatives and nearby Udayagiri to admire the religious monuments that were constructed under her father's patronage. Later she must have kept close contacts with her brother Ghaṭotkaca when he was stationed in Vidiśā, and she may have occasionally visited his court to see her daughter. It seems more than likely that the grandeur of the western capital of the Gupta empire and the artistic achievements of the religious monuments in its surroundings, such as Udayagiri, made a lasting impression on the ambitious Gupta princess. Once in power at Nandivardhana, she decided not to lag behind, but to construct her own holy mountain, the showpiece of her faith in the God, Bhagavat, by whose grace she professed to rule. Thus the temple complex on the

Rāmāgiri came into being. Two attempts were made to excavate caves in the mountain, but they were eclipsed by a better idea, to build structural temples on top of the hill, five of which still stand. Central in this group is the huge image of the boar, Varāha, the rescuer of the earth. But unlike his Udayagiri counterpart, this Varāha is completely theriomorphic and no anthropomorphic supplicant Nāga king is shown at his feet, a royal allegory that served well the Gupta kings, but not the proud daughter of a Nāga princess.¹⁵ Instead the world serpent is unassumingly sculptured as the support of the deity and the world that he sustains. The Udayagiri Temple I has its counterpart in the so-called Bhogarāma Temple on the Rāmāgiri, albeit that the colonnade of the former is extended to six pillars in the latter.¹⁶ The semi-anthropomorphic Narasiṃha, found in Udayagiri for instance at Cave 12 in relief (Fig. 1), assumed majestic form in two temples on the Rāmāgiri, reflecting, as I have argued elsewhere, the power of Prabhāvati's deceased husband, Rudrasena.¹⁷

At the foot of this sacred hill-turned-into-state sanctuary was the residence of the Eastern Vākāṭakas, known from their inscriptions as Nandivardhana and identified with the present village of Nagardhan. Little remains to testify to the former glory of the place, but it may be more than coincidence, contrary to what I suggested in my *Vākāṭaka* book (Bakker 1997), that the three images found there represent an iconographic programme that is seen several times in Udayagiri, for instance in Cave VI, namely the not fully understood juxtaposition of Gaṇeśa, Viṣṇu and Devī Mahiṣāsūramardini.¹⁸

In this way arose in the Waingangā Plain something that was consciously conceived of as a worthy equivalent of Gupta magnificence, not slavishly copied, stylistically different, continuing the sculptural tradition found in earlier cult centres within the Vākāṭaka kingdom such as Mandhal, but all the same, inspired by the artistic achievements of their imperial contemporaries.

After her long rule as regent for her sons, Prabhāvati Gupta continued to play an important role in the affairs of the kingdom. This follows from charters of land donations made by her in the nineteenth and twentieth regnal year of her son Pravarasena II.¹⁹ Pravarasena II thus ruled for at least twenty years with this extraordinary mother at his side (A.D. 422-443), a mother who, no doubt, will have ensured that relations with the mighty northern neighbour, her brother Kumāragupta, remained good. It is all the more noticeable that Pravarasena had returned to the faith of his ancestors. In the six inscriptions that we have of him pertaining to the period that his mother was still alive he styles himself as a *paramamāheśvara*, who by Śiva's grace

2. View of the Rāmagiri from the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

carried the lance (*śūla*) instead of the discus (*cakra*).²⁰ And perhaps even more conspicuous, at a certain stage of his rule he had begun to issue his charters no longer from Nandivardhana, but from a residence called Pravaraपुरा, evidently named after himself. Whereas the location of Nandivardhana is uncontested, at the foot of the Rāmagiri, the site of Pravaraपुरा was, until recently, controversial. Archaeological explorations near the village of Mansar, a village situated 5 km west of Ramtek Hill, has, it would seem, put an end to this controversy. For the continuing story of Prabhāvatī's son, Pravarasena, we have to turn to Mansar.²¹

The Heydays: Pravaraपुरा (Mansar)

To the east of the village of Mansar is a hillock known today as Hiḍimbā Tekḍī, from the top of which one has a direct view of Rāmagiri due east (Fig. 2). Since the beginning of last century the hillock has drawn the attention of scholars because of an inscription in 'shell script' (*sankhalipi*), found on the face of the rock of the western slope (Figs. 3 & 4), like the shell script inscriptions in Udayagiri (Fig. 1), probably meant as a sort of ornamentation or signature. However, the hill only became well-known after 1972, when a splendid sculpture, referred to as the Mansar Śiva (Fig. 5) was found here. Previously Mansar had yielded some stone sculptures that have since disappeared,²² and a set of five Vākātaka copperplates, the whereabouts of four of which are unknown. One plate however was saved and published by Mirashi under the misleading name of *Rāmṭek Plate of Pravarasēna II*.²³

Mainly on the basis of this evidence, I advanced the hypothesis that the supposed Śiva temple on this hill should perhaps be identified as Pravareśvara, a sanctuary known from a charter issued by king Pravarasena II when his residence was still at Nandivardhana, and one that was important enough to possess some land.²⁴ In the eleventh regnal year of this king a resident of the 26th *vāṭaka* of Pravareśvara, Sūryasvāmin, was the recipient of a grant.²⁵ As a corollary of this hypothesis I conjectured that the area around this hill may have been the royal residence Pravaraपुरा, to which this king and his court eventually moved.²⁶ This move may account for the fact that the Pravareśvara temple had acquired the status of a state sanctuary by the end of Pravarasena's rule. From this state (*vaijayikadharmasthāna*) sanctuary, called 'Pravareśvaradevakulasthāna', a charter was issued in his 29th regnal year (c. A.D. 451), in which four brahmins belonging to the Vājasaneyya branch of the White Yajurveda are mentioned as the donees of a landgrant.²⁷ When I wrote my *Vākātaka* book I could not have hoped that the hypothesis advanced would be put to the test so soon. Excavations in Mansar in recent years – by the Department of Ancient Indian History, Culture and Archaeology of the Nagpur University, by the Archaeological Survey of India under the direction of Dr Amarendra Nath, and the present excavations at the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī itself carried out by J.P. Joshi and A.K. Sharma (ASI) – have established beyond doubt that the site around this hill was an important habitation area in the fifth century A.D.²⁸ The excavation by the University of Nagpur in 1989 (under the direction of Dr Ismail

3. Western Slope of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī (before the excavation).

4. Shell script inscription on the western slope of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

5. The Mansar Śiva.

6. Brick structures excavated by Dr Nath c. 100 m east of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

Kellellu) at the foot of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī (now called MNS-1) has not been published, but Joshi & Sharma report that some 'very impressive brick structures' were found (EM 127).

Dr Nath excavated (part of) the western side of a mound (now called MNS-2), situated approximately one hundred metres east of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī, exposing a large brick structure of unusual plan (Fig. 6). A short report was published in IAR 1994-95 [2000], 55-7. According to this report:

These cuttings have revealed a portion of massive burnt-brick structural complex in mud-masonry with *ratha* projections, tentatively showing three phases of constructional activities. The structural activities of phase 1 have been noticed in the cuttings H7, H8 and G7, comprising core area, showing the western elevation of a moulded *adhiṣṭhāna*, couple of *sopānas*, *pradakṣiṇapatha* and an entrance to the complex. ...The entire complex seems to have been enclosed by a *prākāra* wall with low balustrade entrance in the corner of western wall. In the second phase of construction, the *adhiṣṭhāna* seems to have been enlarged without disturbing the original ground plan of core area. ...In phase III, the *sopānas* leading to the floor of *adhiṣṭhāna* were found closed by raising regular walls across them and ultimately filled with brick-bats. Above the *adhiṣṭhāna*, portions of a porch and subsidiary shrines on its northern and eastern segments have been noticed. (IAR 1994-95, p. 56)

Furthermore this excavation yielded "sealed clay images", "a few large-sized standing clay images of divinities and *dvārapālas*", "sculptured objects from the porch and shrine floors" – "Umā-Maheśvara, Lajjāgaurī", "plaque depicting *pādapīṭha*" and "a sizable number of clay figurines" (ibid, p. 56f.). To judge by the illustrations in the report (Plates XXXI-XXXIII), these last concern minor figures or figurines who may have adorned (house) altars, with the intriguing exception of the "moulded human skull", called "head portion of a divine figure in clay" in the caption of Plate XXXII B of the report. The site is rich in "vases", "storage-vases", various types of bowls, diverse ornaments, and an array of iron implements (ibid, p. 56f.). "On the basis of numismatic data" – "a silver portrait coin and a couple of coin-moulds, attributed to the Kshatrapas", "a few circular copper coins, one attributed to the Vākāṭakas and the other to the Indo-Sassanians" – the site was tentatively "assigned to a period between A.D. 300 and 650" (ibid, p. 57). The complex seems to have been destroyed by fire. Some stray coins apart,²⁹ the absence of Sātavāhana coinage on the one hand and the presence of earthenware of "gritty micaceous red ware of coarse fabric and polished red ware of fine fabric" on the other seem indicative of the site being "Vākāṭaka". No temple images such as those found at the nearby Hiḍimbā Tekḍī were recovered from this site. Hence the conclusion that

7. Hiḍimbā Tekḍī excavations. Entrance eastern side.

we are concerned with a sacred complex seems premature. The present excavators, Sharma and Joshi, intend to excavate this mound further from its eastern side; until this has been carried out we shall not know for certain with what kind of building we are here concerned. However, it may cautiously be suggested that, in view of the fact that the great majority of the artefacts could belong to any household, the hypothesis that we may have hit upon a residential building, the royal palace (?), deserves serious consideration.³⁰

The first phase of the excavations at the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī itself, MNS-3, under the direction of J.P. Joshi and A.K. Sharma lasted from January to March 1998.³¹ The second phase started on December 26 of the same year and was still going on in March 1999, when I visited the site. The third field season took place in the winter of 2000. The excavations, licensed by the ASI, take place under the auspices of and are partly financed by the Bodhisattva Nāgārjuna Smārak Saṁsthān or Centre of Buddhist Archaeology (Nagpur); this organisation, which owns the land on and around the hill, also built a museum at the site, in which the images are kept.³²

When I read a paper about this site at the *South Asian Archaeology* conference in Leiden in 1999, I had the good fortune of having my hypothetical identification confirmed by Prof. Ajay Mitra Shastri, who reported that after my visit to the site sealings had been found in the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī excavation reading "Pravareśvara".³³ The finding of the sealings is confirmed in the report on

this excavation that was recently published by Joshi and Sharma (EM):

The most noteworthy find is the factory site of clay sealing on the north-eastern corner, just at the base of the northern row of shrines. The baked clay sealing bear the legend in box-headed *Brahmi* character, reading 'Pravareśvarasya' (fig. 1)... Apart from a number of sealing that bear the legend 'Pravareśvarasya' and 'Shri Jaiṁrdhi', some sealings depict elephant, the animal that appears to have been of great importance to the 'EasternVakatakas'.³⁴

The excavators distinguish three periods. An early one which they date to the 2nd century BC to 250 A.D., a Vākāṭaka one (250 to 500 A.D.) and a third period dating from circa 500 to 700 A.D.. This periodisation is not given a scientific basis by a stratigraphic account of the digging of any sort and thus appears questionable. To the first period the excavators ascribe *inter alia* the brick remains of three *stūpas* (EM 128):

The early *stūpa* also found in the central area was having extant four to five courses of bricks measuring 48x25x8 cm in size. This earliest *stūpa* (Stupa 1) was having a dia of 8 m. Not much could be said about its superstructure as its three sides were superimposed with massive later structures which could not be removed. This *stūpa* was later enlarged by using bricks of the size 42x22x7 cm (Stupa-2).³⁵ It was increased by making brick boxes filled with earth and small boulders, a technique of building *stūpa* also found at Pauni. The present available height

8. Umā-Maheśvara image, Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

9. Kinnara, Hiđimbā Tekđi.

10. Head of a male ascetic, Hiđimbā Tekđi.

II. Liṅga shrine at the south-western corner of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

thus achieved was 2 m in the peripheral area and 3.6 m in the central area of the *stūpa* boxes. The approximate dia of the *stūpa* is 14 m. It has a brick *pradakṣiṇapatha* around it and a rectangular projection is also available in the eastern side. ...Another *stūpa* (Stupa-3) roughly roundish in shapes of undressed boulders having a dia of 11 m with an extant height of 2.70 m has 7-8 courses of undressed stones. It has a Pradakshina path of 1 m wide which has been built right over the northern wall of the last box of the Stupa-2. This *stūpa* came into disuse along with Stupa-2.

There is no denying that the natural hillock is covered by several layers of large brick constructions (Fig. 7). However, neither I nor any other scholar who has been to the site whom I could consult has been able to distinguish anything remotely resembling a *stūpa* in the remains of terraces and walls. To endorse their Buddhist identification the excavators adduce the finding of “a fragment of a soap-stone relic-casket along with a lid fragment” recovered from the “peripheral area of this *stūpa*” (i.e. Stupa 2). There is little to corroborate their contention that we are here concerned with a reliquary rather than with an ordinary stone casket, which could have been used for all sorts of purposes. Not a single Buddhist image or artefact has come to light so far. The hypothesis that ascribes the lower brick layers to a *stūpa* is therefore open to serious doubt. This doubt is only aggravated by the fact that the excavators ascribe (EM 128) to the same period, albeit to the end of it, “two sacrificial altars, one in the shape of a *śyena-citi* and the other a *kūrma-citi*, made of bricks” and “the figure of a Puruṣa made of lime” (see below). Adjoining the so-called *kūrma-citi* the excavators describe a “small *havana-kunḍa*, a lime kiln and a square shrine made of

bricks which apparently appears to have been a Śaiva shrine as there is a hole for outlet of water.” The lack of drawings of the actual layers, plans and stratigraphic charts makes this hotch potch, in which Buddhist, Vedic and Śaiva material apparently alternate pell-mell, fail to carry conviction. To the earliest layers of the site may also belong some finds which are described under the heading “Period II”, e.g. “an earlier inscription datable to 2nd century B.C.” (EM 130). Unfortunately we do not learn more about this ancient inscription.³⁶ In the Site Museum I saw a fragment of a sprinkler of Red Polished Ware (not mentioned in the report),³⁷ which could, possibly, be dated to the 3rd century AD, but it may also be later. It should further be noted, that, unlike some other Buddhist sites in Vidarbha, like Pauni for instance, none of the three excavations in Mansar has, to the best of my knowledge, yielded Sātavāhana coins so far. In sum, the whole of Joshi and Sharma’s “First period” may be an illusion.

The second period distinguished by the excavators, the Vākāṭaka period, is characterised by

a magnificent temple with plinth of dressed sand stone blocks and supper structure of bricks built by the Vakatakas. This temple with two phases of construction has yielded many fragmentary sculptures having impressive headdress and bedecked with jewellery. These are in the best traditions of the Vakataka art...

North-south width of the temple is 12.60 m. In order to strengthen the northern and southern slopes of the hillock massive pitching walls were raised to an extent of 60 m on each side, using huge boulders. Due to this pitching the temple complex would have looked like a fortress. (EM 128f.)

Though obviously much of the original temple walls remain, the excavators note that a “major part of the temple complex is concealed under the walls of the later *stūpa*” (EM 129). This later *stūpa* must be Stupa 4, which is believed to belong to a Period III and was “built at the top and remained in existence till the end of the 7th century A.D” (EM 131). The report gives the impression that some walls are counted twice, once as temple walls, then again as *stūpa* “walls”. Many (fragments of) images have been found, all Hindu in nature. Among the most impressive ones is a fragment of an Umā-Maheśvara image, of which only Śiva’s head and the arm of his spouse around his neck is preserved (Fig. 8). This beautiful sculpture is carved out of the same red sandstone as the Mansar Śiva and some of the sculptures of the Rāmagiri area. Another impressive image is that of a Kinnara made of chert stone (head is missing), showing the rotund body that is the hallmark of the Vākāṭaka art (Fig. 9). Several stocky torsos and loose heads of red sandstone have been uncovered, among which the head of a male ascetic (Śiva?) with flower cap (Fig. 10). Among the other striking features of the site is a series of small

Above
12. Detail of the *linga* of Fig. 11 showing *pārsavasūtra* and *brahmasūtra*.

Below
13. Area of the brick 'altars' and Man of Mansar (covered).
Photograph Yuko Yokochi.

Top right
14. The man of Mansar made of clay, Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

15. Brick construction at the northern side interpreted by Joshi and Sharma as an Agnicayana altar in the form of a hawk (*śyena*ci).

liṅga shrines. There are six *liṅgas* exposed, situated half-way along the southern and western slopes of the hill. They are installed on square platforms and enshrined (encapsulated rather) in brick constructions of an intricate pattern featuring projecting and receding surfaces (Fig. 11). The excavators report that ten more shrines have been uncovered, without *liṅgas*. The peculiar form of these shrines is described as follows:

Vertically all the shrines have been built in the form of 'lotus buds' by adopting the triangles and inverted triangles (equilateral). Method for raising petals, that ultimately close into a pointed end making the close roof of the *Sikhara* has been adopted [sic]. The evidence clearly shows that the whole complex was plastered with lime mortar. (EM 129f.)

Though most of the *liṅgas* are eroded, one of them still clearly shows a *pārśvasūtra* and *brahmasūtra* (Fig. 12), in a style that best resembles type e as presented by Mitterwallner (1984, p. 19) ("Deogarh, UP, from Rājghāṭī, ca. early sixth century A.D."). We may tentatively deduce from this that these *liṅgas* belong to the Vākāṭaka period, not earlier, and probably not later; that is, they are rightly ascribed to Period II and seem to be an integral part of the overall Vākāṭaka construction and more or less contemporaneous with the other sculptures. On account of this new evidence my earlier observation (Bakker 1997, p. 75) to the effect that "Māheśvara worship of the elite in the Vākāṭaka

kingdom was iconic, not aniconic or semi-aniconic" is to be reconsidered.

The most spectacular part of this site, however, is the area in which the two putative altars are found next to the more than life-size figure of a man made of clay (Figs. 13 and 14):

After an accumulation of 1.25 m deposit, at the end of the Satvahana period and beginning of the Vakataka period two sacrificial altars, one in the shape of a *śyena-citi* and the other a *kūrma-citi*, made of bricks have been exposed [at the southern side]. The *śyena-citi* which is in the north was made after smashing the cross-walls of the earlier *stūpa* which has gone out of the use by that time making the ground levelled. In the *śyena-citi*, [a] figure of a Puruṣa made of lime has been found sacrificed with his head smashed. The head of the figure is oriented towards west, whereas the legs are put towards east. A *vedi* in the chest portion with a hole for fixing a *yaṣṭi* over it was made and an earthen lamp was found kept nearby. Two pots have also been kept near the knee region of the figure which lies on his right side with an iron snake kept near his left toe, looking towards the human figure. (EM 128)

A plan or drawing of these brick 'altars' in which the forms of a hawk (*śyena*) and turtle (*kūrma*) are lined out would have been helpful. The present author has to admit that neither during his stay at the site, nor afterwards while studying photographic documentation, has he been able to discover any animal form, or

16. Iron snake at the left foot of the clay figure, Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.

whatever other form for that matter, in these extraordinary brick constructions (Fig. 15). What I did see, however, were workers who, while the excavations were still going on, were engaged in “restoring” the dilapidated walls with the help of stray bricks and mortar (Fig. 18). Although the excavators avoid mentioning it explicitly in their report, the idea behind the alleged “altars” and “sacrificed *puruṣa*” is that we are here concerned with an Agnicayana altar, which, as is well known, may have the form of a hawk.³⁹ This idea, which raises the subject of the Vedic ritual of the piling up of the fire-altar, deserves serious consideration. An outline of the major features of the Agnicayana altar and its ritual construction is presented in Appendix II

Romila Thapar (in *Agni II*, pp. 2-40) examined the archaeological sites that have been connected with the Agnicayana altar. These sites are few “and of these only one is accepted as genuine, since it carries an inscription describing it as an altar” (ibid, p. 26), viz. the altar found in Jagatgram in the Dehra Dun district.³⁸ Here “three sites were exposed where a king had performed Aśvamedhas. Each site consisted of an eagle-shaped altar. Inscribed bricks from the first site provide the information that a king, Śīlavarman, performed four Aśvamedhas at Jagatgram” (ibid, p. 34). Comparison with Mansar shows that the constructions in the two places are very different. One of the conspicuous differences is that the Jagatgram altars were built in an open field (*kṣetra*), as one would indeed expect. Another place that has been associated with an Agnicayana altar was found at the excavations in Kausambi. “The archaeological data” of this site, as described by G.R. Sharma (1960), “clearly reveal a ritual altar of the shape of a flying bird”.⁴¹ Within the five layers of the altar “a large number of human skulls and bones of animals of different species, meticulously aranged” were found.⁴² In layer one the excavators found, inter alia, a “human skull”, “the shell of a tortoise” and “the iron model of a

17. Iron snake found in Kausambi.
(from Sharma 1960, Plate 43 No.38).

snake”.⁴³ Layer three “yielded the largest number of bones with a preponderance of human bone”: “three complete human skulls, ten skull pieces and other skeletal material”.⁴⁴ Summarizing Sharma states that “there is sufficient evidence to conclude that this fire altar was piled up for the performance of the *Puruṣamedha*”.⁴⁵

Sharma’s conclusions have been challenged by von Schlingloff (1968-69). The latter’s criticism is in particular directed against the alleged historicity of the human sacrifice (*puruṣamedha*).⁴⁶ Romila Thapar’s criticism takes a different route. It is not so much that she doubts the historicity of the *puruṣamedha*, but that she calls the ‘fire altar’ itself into question.

The identification of the site as a fire altar does raise some problems. The location of the altar so close to the ramparts of the city seems unusual. ...The shape of the bird as presently reconstructed appears to be rather curvilinear, whereas the bricks used for the altar would indicate a more rectilinear form. The interpretation of the objects found is also not convincing. ...nor is the iron model of the snake recognizable. ...The frequency of human skulls and bones would also seem to suggest a ritual different from that described in the texts and it certainly is in excess of what is required. ...there can be little doubt that the structure did represent some kind of sacrificial or funerary site.⁴⁷

Whatever doubts one may have concerning the Kausambi excavation, it is obvious that it is one of the main sites that should be compared with that of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī. If anything, this is apparent from the figure of the iron snake found in Mansar at the bottom of the brick construction near the left foot of the clay figure (Fig. 16), which so much resembles the ‘iron model’ of Kausambi (Fig. 17), that Thapar’s doubts in this respect can be laid to rest.⁴⁸ However, as far as I know, no skulls or bones were found in the altar area of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī.⁴⁹

A comparison of the actual finds on the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī with the textual prescriptions for the ritual construction of the Agnicayana altar, including the

18. Brick construction on top of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī, interpreted as a stūpa (Stupa-4) by Joshi and Sharma.

implied *puruṣamedha*, raises more questions than it solves (see Appendix II), just as this is the case in the other archaeological sites associated with such an altar, with the possible exception of Jagatgram. There are plenty of elements that do not fit the textual descriptions. For instance, the iron snake directed towards the *puruṣa* is not the same as the head of a real snake turned away from (the skulls of) the sacrificial victims; according to the texts the head of the human figure should have been situated in the east instead of the west; the square surface with a hole in the middle on the man's breast, the so-called *vedi* (Fig. 14), does not correspond to anything known from the Agnicayana texts. The sacrificial pole (*yaṣṭi* or *yūpa*), according to the Śrautasūtras, should be at the eastern edge of the altar, etc. etc. The greatest difficulty, however, is presented by the fact that the brick constructions around the clay man are not recognizable as an altar and certainly not as one that consists of (only) five layers of peculiarly shaped bricks.

Other interpretations are possible, though this is not the place to elaborate extensively on them. One is that we are here concerned with a revalorization of the human sacrifice that was, according to the White Yajurveda tradition, once part of the construction of the Agnicayana altar, but now transformed into a construction or foundation sacrifice in the context of temple/house building. The human being, or its clay substitute, may have been thought necessary, not only to confer strength to the building but also, as in the case of

the altar, to integrate the temple building into the cosmic reality of the divine *puruṣa*. Hard evidence for this type of rituals in India is meagre, but recently Jordaan and Wessing (1999) have argued in an article, entitled *Construction Sacrifice* in India "seen from the East", that the practice of construction sacrifices (*vāstuyajña*) in South-Asia must have been widespread, as it was in South-east Asia. In this respect the "head portion of a divine figure in clay" found by Dr Nath in MNS-2 may be significant as it may have formed part of a larger figure comparable to the one found in MNS-3 and like the latter it may have served in a house-building ritual.

Amita Ray surveyed various house-buildings rituals in ancient India. She came to the following conclusion:

In all these [rituals], carrying and establishment of fire to and at the site and inside the building, offering the sacrifices to the spirits and the lord of the *Vāstu*, the firm post symbolising the *Vāstoṣpati*, the hole and filling it in with earth and slabs of stone and brick, entering the house with wife etc. ...are common to all levels and stages of society.⁵⁰

The Lord of the Homestead, *Vāstoṣpati*, already present in the hymns of the *Ṛgveda* 7.54.1-3, is represented by a firm post and one wonders whether the hole in the "vedi" on the breast of the clay figure may not once have held such a post. According to Vedic domestic ritual "an offering (*sthālīpāka* cooked in milk) is made to

Vāstoṣpati with the incantation 'drive away evil; make our wealth increase; protect us always etc'."⁵¹ This line of thought leads us into the concept of the "Man of the Homestead" Vāstupuruṣa, which, as opposed to what has generally been held, may actually have had a practical side to it, that is, it may have been part of a sort of *vāstuśamana* or *śanti* rite. Thus Varāhamihira (mid 6th century) begins his chapter on Architecture with the following two verses, after having said that the science of house-building (*vāstujñāna*) came down from Brahmā:

To be more precise, there was a being that by his body obstructed the earth and the sky, that being was forcibly seized by the immortals, who felled him, head-down. And wherever a god held it, there that god became established; the Creator ordained that the House Man (*vāstu-nara*) was to consist of those immortals.⁵²

The primary and secondary literature on the Vāstupuruṣa and the related concept of the Vāstunāga is too extensive to allow adequate treatment in the present context. Suffice it to say that the idea of the Vāstupuruṣamaṇḍala, the diagram in which the contours of the macro-microcosmic Man is marked and which is supposed to underly the Hindu temple, is first and foremost a theoretical concept, which had hardly, if at all, demonstrable effects on the actual architecture of the temple, or its archaeology for that matter.⁵³ However, excavations by Dhavalikar and Jamkhedkar elsewhere in Maharashtra, in Kandhar (Nanded district), c. 350 km south-west of Mansar, brought to light

remains of a unique stone structure which is human shaped (22 m long and 7 m wide) and enclosed by a double stone wall (37 m x 33 m). It is provided with an entrance on the east. It is for the first time that such type of structure has been found in the subcontinent and it answers well to the description of Vāstu-puruṣa given in Śilpa texts which often compare the dwelling of the god with the human body *puruṣa*. ...The structure is built of dressed stones in mud masonry, the intervening space being filled in with pebbles. ...The head portion, which is in the north-west, is 6.35 m long and 4.85 m wide. The legs, which are in the south-east direction, are 10.88 m long and their maximum width at the thigh is 2.20 m. ...Near the legs was noticed a circular pit, which is now full of fallen stones."

Though the size of this Puruṣa and its fabric is entirely different from the clay figure found in Mansar, the direction of head and legs to some extent agree.⁵⁵

To conclude our examination of the Man of Mansar we may observe that in the present state of our knowledge a conclusive interpretation cannot be given. The meaning and function of this figure, the ceremony with which it was installed, and the purpose of its makers may have comprised elements from all three interpretation schemes that we have discussed: the

reintegration of man and God through the sacrificial insertion of a (substitute) human figure into the brick fundamentals of a sacred building, the idea of a (human) sacrifice to safeguard the building and to ward off *genii loci*, and the idea of conjoining micro- and macrocosmos.

Joshi and Sharma distinguish a third period, post-Vākāṭaka (500–700 AD), in which

The Buddhists finally built a *stūpa* (Stupa-4) having 24 brick built boxes with a central box filled with rubble and stones. It is having a diameter of 18 m and steps on the eastern side. This large *stūpa* was built at the top and remained in existence till the end of 7th century A.D. (EM 131)

The interpretation of these brick constructions (Fig. 18) as another *stūpa* is open to the same doubt as the earlier putative *stūpas*. One is particularly sceptical because some of the Hindu sculptures seem to have been recovered from exactly this top layer at the south-western end of the hillock, among which the Mansar-Śiva of the National Museum.⁵⁶

There are good reasons to assume that the latter sculpture once was one of the major images of the Pravareśvara temple (Fig. 5). It defies identification as one specific form of Śiva or Maheśvara, though its identification as an idol of this god is safeguarded by its attributes, such as the rosary, the skull, the crescent, the matted hair etc. The site where the image was found and the sheer quality of the sculpture, both point to royal patronage. Considerations of style lead to a dating of the image in the second quarter of the fifth century and thus connect it with the time that Pravarasena II built his new residence Pravarapura, a move that may have sealed the process in which the king broke away from his mother and her Bhāgavata milieu. At the same time the Pravareśvara sanctuary may have entered its second phase of construction (above p. 11), in which it developed into the principal state sanctuary. The iconological analysis of this image given by me elsewhere (Bakker 1997, p. 5) seems to support this conjecture.⁵⁷

The Latter Years of Pravarasena's Rule

We have described the rise of Vākāṭaka culture in the first half of the 5th century, as attested by the state sanctuary on the Rāmagiri, and we have looked at Udayagiri as a likely source of inspiration. After the changing of the guard, when Pravarasena had taken over from his mother, we saw the coming into being of the new residence Pravarapura and its state sanctuary Pravareśvara. The buildings uncovered in Mansar mark the heydays of the Eastern Vākāṭakas. The new royal centre evidently meant to counter balance the old queen-mother's formidable authority in matters of the state and religion, if not also in the personal sphere. There are

indications that the death of this extraordinary woman in about A.D. 443 brought about a significant change in Vākāṭaka policies, policies which, to the taste of ambitious princes, may have tended too much towards subservience to Gupta will. In an inscription dating from Pravarasena's twenty-third regnal year, i.e. soon after his mother's death, we encounter the first evidence that the Vākāṭaka king had entered into the territories of his uncle, the kingdom of Kumāragupta. These so-called Indore Plates were issued from the royal camp in Tripurī, the ancient capital of the Dahala country on the northern bank of the Narmada river.⁵⁸ A problematic verse in the Bhitārī Stone Pillar Inscription of Skandagupta, in which this king records how he, already during the reign of his father Kumāragupta, had rescued the shaken fortunes of his family by vanquishing and subduing his enemies (CII III, 315 vs. 4), may refer to this emerging conflict. The anonymous enemies, Mirashi argued, included the Vākāṭakas.⁵⁹

Pravarasena's intrusion into Gupta territory and the response of prince Skandagupta may be seen as a prelude to the war that broke out in North India during the fifties of the 5th century, in which the tensions between the Guptas and Vākāṭakas apparently came to a head. At the death of Kumāragupta in A.D. 454, Pravarasena became mixed up in the war between Ghaṭotkaca and Skandagupta. We learn about this war from the Bhitārī Stone Pillar Inscription; Mirashi argued convincingly that the verses 4 to 8 of this inscription "refer to three different struggles in which Skandagupta was involved", viz. (1) hostilities between Pravarasena and the Guptas while Kumāragupta was still alive, (2) the war of succession, and (3) Skandagupta's struggle with the Hūṇas.⁶⁰

Although history does not repeat itself, geographical patterns of spheres of influence may repeatedly produce power struggles that are structurally akin. Eastern Malwa, with its important centres of Vidiśā and Airikīṇa (Eran), had been the scene of an uprising against the authority of the imperial centre, when Candragupta II ousted his rival Rāmagupta after the death of Samudragupta.⁶¹ At the end of Kumāragupta's reign a similar power struggle appears to have taken place. The viceroy of Vidiśā, Ghaṭotkaca, contested the right to the imperial throne of his nephew Skandagupta, a bastard of his brother Kumāragupta. In these struggles between the western and eastern halves of the Gupta empire, the viceroys of Vidiśā may have been supported by Nāga feudatories, who had not yet forgotten their defeat by Samudragupta and were biding their time. Verse 2 of Skandagupta's Junagadh Rock Inscription alludes to this, when it refers to Skandagupta as the one "who forged an order with an effigy, namely Garuḍa, which rendered, devoid of poison, the Serpent Rulers [i.e. the Nāgas], who uplifted their hoods in pride and

arrogance."⁶² In all probability, Pravarasena in this conflict stood at the side of his brother-in-law (who happened also to be his maternal uncle), with the result that the old Vākāṭakas-Vidiśā-Nāga axis, nourished by his mother Prabhāvatī, became re-established in order to ward off once again the imperial claims of the ruler of the Doab on the rich plains of Eastern Malwa. The Kevala-Narasimha Temple Inscription provides further evidence for this hypothesis. As we have seen above (P. 3), the ruler of Vidiśā, Skandagupta's uncle and rival to the throne Ghaṭotkaca, was married to a Vākāṭaka princess, his niece (*bhāginēyī*) to be precise. The inscription reports that, after the fall of Ghaṭotkaca, the brother of his wife, who can hardly be other than Pravarasena II, "brought her home by force".⁶³ The most plausible interpretation of this extraordinary piece of evidence seems to be that Pravarasena, having joined the side of Ghaṭotkaca, when the alliance had been defeated, prevented his widowed sister from being confined by her Gupta in-laws by bringing her back to the haunts of her youth, at which remarkable feat he might have profited from the fact that Skandagupta was engaged in a protracted struggle with the Hūṇas.⁶⁴

The dramatic events told in the Ramtek Inscription, since they seem to coincide with Skandagupta's war of succession, must have taken place in A.D. 454-5. The expedition may have exhausted Pravarasena and he probably died soon thereafter. This would explain why we do not find allusions to these events in the Vākāṭaka king's own inscriptions, the last one of which dates from his thirty-second regnal year (c. A.D. 454). The reason why Skandagupta in his inscriptions refers to his victory over anonymous enemies (*amitrāmś*) rather than mentioning them by their names, as indeed the Hūṇas are mentioned, may have been dictated by internal political considerations: after all it was his uncle and cousin who had driven him into dire straits. We now understand why Skandagupta after this victory ran towards his anonymous mother, as told in his Bhitārī Pillar Inscription, "which made her weep like Devakī after Kṛṣṇa had killed his enemy", namely his uncle (Kaṁsa).⁶⁵ With this internecine struggle half a century of peace, stability and prosperity in Vidarbha came to a close. Pravarapura lost much of its glory. The unfortunate widow, like her mother, issued her charter from the state sanctuary of the Rāmagiri and so did the latter's great-grandson Prthivīṣeṇa II.

We have come to the end of the story. After the Eastern Vākāṭakas had forfeited the support of their northern neighbours, they soon lost their independence, not to the Guptas however, but to their distant relatives, the rulers in Vatsagulma. Hariṣeṇa was heir to the cultural achievements of the eastern kingdom and turned them into something just as astonishing, the Buddhist caves in Ajanta. But here we enter another time

Appendix I

Gupta – Vākātaka Genealogy

Appendix II

Excursus upon the Construction of the Agnicayana Altar

and another man's territory, where even *vidyādharas* fear to tread: that of the formidable Walter Spink.

The ritual of placing a golden (i.e. immortal) man at the base of the fire-altar is *inter alia* described in *Āpastamba Śrautasūtra* 16.22.3-4. Broadly speaking the procedure is as follows. After preparing the ground of the fire-altar, a knobbed, gold disk or plate is laid on a lotus-leaf; on this (plate) a man of gold is laid, directed towards the East, stretched out on his back, to the right of the hole (in the plate). Then the Puruṣasāman should be sung.⁶⁶ Next, after the golden man has been "touched" by a verse,⁶⁷ the serpents (*sarpa*) should be saluted with three verses.⁶⁸ Ghee is sprinkled over the man. On either side of the man a sacrificial ladle is laid.⁶⁹ Here after the laying of the bricks is begun, the first one being the *soyāmattṛṇṇā* ("the naturally pierced one") placed on the gold man to allow him to breathe. A living tortoise is also built into the altar. Then, after a square mortar (*ulūkhalaka*) made of udumbara wood has been installed at the 'northern shoulder' (*uttare 'mṣe*) (of the

fire-altar) and the fire-pot (*ukhā*) is placed in the middle (*madhye*),⁷⁰ the heads of the five sacrificial victims (*paśus*) are installed: the human head in the middle of the fire-pot, the head of a horse towards the west, of a bull towards the east, of a ram towards the south, and of a goat towards the north, while seven gold pieces are laid in the seven orifices of the human head. Hereafter *Āpastamba* prescribes that a snake head (*sarpaśiras*) should be put on the right shoulder (*dakṣiṇe 'mṣe*, i.e. south side) of the fire-altar (using the 'homage to the serpents' verse), which is turned away from the other sacrificial heads lest, the *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* (5.2.9.5) remarks, it should bite these domesticated animals instead of wild ones.⁷¹ After the snake, *Āpastamba* enjoins that a human figure (*puruṣākṛti*) should be assembled (*cinoti*) by means of twelve 'turns' (*pariyāya*) each spoken thrice, a (virtual?) body stretching from east to west, the head of which coincides with the head of the golden man (*purusaśiras*). The sacrificer gives praise to this construction (*upahitā*) by the Puruṣa Nārāyaṇa.⁷²

Though they seem to differ with respect to where exactly the *puruṣa* and the *sarpaśiras* are to be constructed,⁷³ both Black Yajurveda branches (the Maitrāyaṇīyas and Taittirīyas) differ from the Vājasaneyins (represented by the *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa* and *Kātyāyana Śrautasūtra*) in that Śrautasūtras of both traditions prescribe this human figure and serpent head to be part of the first layer of the fire-altar. However, the idiosyncrasy of this part of the ritual is evident in the alternative allowed by two Śrautasūtras (Āpastamba and Mānava) to constructing the serpent head only virtually, by means of formulas, and the omission of the human figure in Baudhāyana.⁷⁴

It is clear that the central role of the human head (and the four animal heads) in the piling up of the fire-altar presupposes sacrificial slaughter of some sort. According to the Śrautasūtras of the Black Yajurveda, the human head should be cut off of a kṣatriya or vaiśya killed by an arrow or lightning,⁷⁵ after which it has to be covered with clay and set aside.⁷⁶ The tradition of the White Yajurveda is more explicit that this ritual requires a human sacrifice. The *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa* (6.2.1.18) unambiguously declares that "a man (*puruṣa*) should be sacrificed first, for man is the first of the sacrificial animals (*paśu*)". The *Kātyāyana Śrautasūtra* states that the victim, a vaiśya or rājanya (16.1.17), should be suffocated in a special secluded place,⁷⁷ after which his head is taken (16.1.18), though it allows the option that a head of gold or clay is used as a substitute.⁷⁸ This may have become common practice when animal sacrifice, not to speak of human sacrifice, had become taboo. The bodies of the four animal victims are thrown into the water from where the clay is taken to make the bricks.⁷⁹ What is done with the decapitated human corpse remains unclear in the Śrautasūtras. The *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa* strongly suggests that all trunks are thrown into the water:⁸⁰ "As to these glories,⁸¹ they are these very heads of the sacrificial victims and these trunks are the five (altar) layers (*citi*). Therefore, after having placed the heads of the sacrificial victims, one piles up the layers; then one unites these trunks with these same heads."⁸² Though the obvious interpretation takes the layers as a substitute for the trunks, it cannot be excluded that, in particular in the case of the human *paśu*, the body of the victim was, occasionally perhaps, interred into the altar, by which the *puruṣa* (Prajāpati and sacrificial victim and *yajamāna*) became reintegrated in the sacrificial sphere, a reintegration that is the alpha and the omega of the Agnicayana, as reflected, for instance in the golden man. In total the altar consists of five layers of brick, which may have the shape of a bird, especially the *śyena* (hawk), which is standard, but optionally also that of a triangle, a chariot-wheel, a trough, a circle, or a burial mound (i.e. square).⁸³ When this brick altar has been completed the *āhavanīya* fire is established on it.

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Though I see it as my duty to assess the results of their excavation critically, I wish to express my sincere gratitude to J.P. Joshi and A.K. Sharma, who have given me access without restriction to their excavation in Mansar and allowed me to take photographs. I have greatly profited from the scholarly spirit in which they have brought their findings up for discussion. *Dubitando ad veritatem pervenimus*.

NOTES

- 1 Bakker 1997, 9f.
- 2 Shastri 1992. Cf. Bakker 1997, 12ff. See however below n. 57 on p. 22.
- 3 Kevala-Narasimha Temple Inscription (Bakker 1997, 164) vs. 5 (l. 3).
- 4 Poona Plates of Prabhāvati-guptā (CII V, 7) ll. 6-8 (cf. *ibid.* 36 ll. 7-9).
- 5 Sircar 1967 I, pp. 204-9, 236; 1987, p. 26. The suggestion by Ashvini Agrawal (1989, p. 83) to read *dhāraṇasagotra-nāgakulotpannāyām* instead of *dhāraṇasagotrā-nāgakulotpannāyām* is not supported by the text of the inscription which clearly reads *sagotrā* followed by hiatus. A brahmin belonging to the Dhāraṇi *gotra* was the recipient of a grant by the Paramabhaṭṭāraka (EI XXXI, 263-268).
- 6 Bakker 1997, 15f.
- 7 Poona Plates of Prabhāvati-guptā (CII V, 7 l. 9).
- 8 CII V, 7 ll. 9-10: *yuvārāja(śrī)DIVĀKRASENAjanaī*. The seal of these Poona Plates of Prabhāvati, issued during the thirteenth year of her regency, runs (CII V, 8): *vākātakalālāmasya (kra) maprāptanṛpaśriya (ḥ) | jananyā yuvārājasya śāsanam ripuśāsa (nam ||)*.
- 9 Divākarasena is no longer mentioned as a son or king in the later charters of Prabhāvati; in his stead two other sons of hers, Dāmodarasena and Pravarasena are called Mahārāja, CII V, 36 l. 10: *vākātakānām mahārājaśrī(ḥ) DĀMODARA-SENAPRAVARASENAjanaī*. That we are here actually concerned with two kings follows from the Miregāon Plates of Prabhāvati Gupta (reign of Pravarasena II, Year 20), published by Shastri & Kawadkar 2001, of which charter the seal reads: *vīkrāntayor jananyās tu vākātakanarendrayo(ḥ) | śrīPRABHĀVATIGUPTAYĀ (ḥ) śāsanam ripuśāsanam ||* (op. cit. p. 151).
- 10 Cf. the succession to the throne of Sarvasena II of the Vatsagulma branch, who was only eight years old when his father died (CII V, 108 vs. 10).
- 11 Kevala-Narasimha Temple Inscription (Bakker 1997, 164f.) vs. 11-13.
- 12 Ghaṭotkaca Gupta was until recently only known from his Tumain inscription of A.D. 435-6, a seal found in Basarh, and two gold coins (ASI Annual Report 1903-04, 107; EI XXVI, 117; CII III, pp. 276-279, 294-296). One of the gold coins is in the St Peterburg Collection (Allan 1914, p. liv, pl. XXIV.3), the other was published by Ajit Ghosh in JNSI 22 (1960), p. 260f., Pl. 9.6. With regard to the St Peterburg coin Thaplyal 1972, 67 remarks that, if this coin was issued by the Ghaṭotkaca of the Tumain Inscription, 'he might also have unsuccessfully contended for the imperial crown against Skandagupta.' This assessment is based on the affinity of the Ghaṭotkaca coins with the Archer coins of variety B struck by Skandagupta (Raven 1994, p. 15 n. 1.31). Thaplyal's conjecture proves to be right, as we will see below.
- 13 Ghaṭotkaca may have been installed by his elder brother Kumāragupta after they had eliminated their (elder) brother Govindagupta (see below n. 61 on p. 22).
- 14 Kane 1930-62 Vol. II, p. 467.
- 15 Cf. Bakker 1997, Plates XXXII A and XLVI.
- 16 Cf. EITA II.1, Plates 11 and 124.
- 17 Bakker 1992, 1997 Plate XXXIII.
- 18 Cf. Bakker 1997, Plates XLIV B, XLVA & B and Plates XXVIII, XXVII, XXIX A.
- 19 Riddhapur Plates of Prabhāvati-guptā (CII V, pp. 33-37) and Miregāon Plates of Prabhāvati Gupta (Shastri & Kawadkar 2001).
- 20 CII V, 12 l. 16, 71 ll. 1-2.
- 21 The village of Mansar (Manasara) is bordered at its eastern side by a lake or water-reservoir on. On the further, eastern side of this lake is the Hiḍimbā Hill. An artificial dam along the southern side of the reservoir connects the village with the hill. A survey of the area (with map) was first presented by Wellsted 1934. At his time the lake apparently extended further to the east, along the northern side of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī. This author also noticed 'the mile-long stone facing of the Mansar tank, drybuilt of large boulders and stone slabs, reaching its greatest development at the monastery site' (i.e. MNS II, see below). The name of the village is thought to derive from the name of the lake. As such is mentioned 'Mānasarovar.' However, Mirashi 1959, p. 22 derives the name from 'Maṇikālasara,' which he thinks was the original name of the lake. The *Ramtek Stone Inscription of the time of Ramachandra* mentions a Maṇikālakuṇḍa (Bakker 1989, p. 484 vs. 75). The (late) *Sindūragirimāhātmya* 2.6 mentions a *tītha* Maṇikāla where a man, after a bath, should worship Hiḍimbā. In the *Sthāna Pothī* (p. 5) of the Mahānubhāva sect a seat of Cakradhara is mentioned called Manasīla.
- 22 Wellsted 1934, p. 161: "During the course of investigations [in 1928] a number of carved stone fragments were found at the surface on the hill slopes to the south of the lake [i.e. on the slopes of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī]." Some of these are illustrated by Wellsted in Plate 11; they appear to be Vākātaka pieces. The same author also illustrates a fragment of an inscribed stone showing parts of four *akṣaras*, apparently in Vākātaka script.
- 23 CII V, pp. 73-75.
- 24 Bakker 1997, 87f., p. 149.
- 25 CII V, 19 ll. 13-14 & 14-15. It is generally assumed that both sets of Belora Plates (A & B), in which the grants to Sūryasvāmin are described, were issued from Nandivardhana in the 11th regnal year of Pravarasena, though set A, which contains the first plate and therefore the place of issue (Nandivardhana), lacks the last plate with the date, while set B, which is dated in the 11th regnal year, misses the first plate and hence the place of issue. The plates have been re-examined by A.M. Shastri (Shastri 1997, pp. 13-16) who came to the conclusion that we are actually concerned with one set only (plate II of set B being a forgery).
- 26 Bakker 1997, 4f.
- 27 This community of White Yajurveda brahmins, presumably living at the southern edge of the Satpura Range in the Chhindwara District (MP), had previously been the recipient of a grant made by Prthivīrāja (i.e. Prthivīśeṇa I, c. A.D. 360-395), since the grant by Pravarasena II was in exchange of another village (Vijayapallivāṭaka), earlier donated by the former king (CII V, 66 ll. 19f.). The recipients of the many landgrants of Pravarasena II are brahmins, with the exception of one Atharvavedin (CII V, 50 l. 18), all Yajurvedins, mostly belonging to the Taittirīya branch, among whom the above-mentioned Sūryasvāmin, resident of the 26th *vāṭaka* of Pravareśvara, and the Adhvaryū Ācārya Devaśarman, recipient of the village Brahmāpūraka (CII V, p. 30).
- 28 Cf. Wellsted 1934, p. 161: "In 1928 a certain amount of interesting material came to light and led to the examination of the whole area surrounding Mansar tank, with the result that the traces of an extensive township were discovered."

- 29 Joshi and Sharma in their report of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī excavation (MNS-3) report the surface find of "a silver coin of western Kshatrpa king showing Swami Rudrasena III's bust on the obverse and on the reverse a caitya with inscriptions reading Maha Kshtrapa Swami Rudradaman Putasa Raja Maha Kshtrapa Swami Rudrasena 21 Saka (348-378 A.D.)". Could it be that this is the same coin as reported by Dr Nath?
- 30 The observations by Wellsted and the plan he provided of the mound itself and its surroundings (in which Wellsted situates the 'outer court') have unfortunately been ignored in the report of Dr Nath, but they are well worth quoting (Wellsted 1934, p. 162): "In the centre is a large mound which rises to a height of 40 ft. above the level and resembles the ruined stump of a Buddhist stupa in its general appearance, an impression which is not confirmed by a close examination, which reveals traces of a rectangular building measuring 150 ft. x 85 ft. in the centre of the mound. It is possibly therefore the remains of a vihāra or even of a secular building with surrounding courts, but whatever its character, which can only be revealed by excavation, it obviously covered a group of buildings of great importance. Until quite recently the site has been used by villagers as a brick quarry, so much so that it has been possible to obtain a very tolerable idea of the ground plan as revealed by this destruction. This is shown in Plate 8." (italics mine). Wellsted gives a brief description of the site and notes that the size of the bricks is c. 17"x9"x3" (45x23x8 cm, cf. above p. 8).
- 31 About this site Wellsted 1934, p. 161f. had observed (ignored by J.P. Joshi and A.K. Sharma): "Hill B was apparently overbuilt with temples and all surface finds of sculpture have come from there. Such as have been found exhibit considerable skill and mastery in execution and from the quantity and diversity of character must represent a very large number of images. The stone used is a fine-grained aluminous sandstone, easy to work and permitting a fine finish." (italics mine).
- 32 This Japan-based Buddhist organisation purchased the land on which the excavations MNS-1, -2, and -3 have been carried out, inspired, it would seem, by the early survey of T.A. Wellsted, who had noticed at the site of MNS-2 "remains of a great monastery" (as cited in IAR 1994-95, 55, EM 127), though Wellsted was actually more cautious in his identification than this citation suggests (see above n. 30). The Hiḍimbā Tekḍī hillock itself was also taken for a stūpa, especially, it would seem, after Dr Nath's excavation of the 'great monastery' at MNS-2 had, disappointedly, not yielded any Buddhist artefact. Long before the present excavations the owners had placed a (new) Buddha image on the top of the hillock to mark its alleged Buddhist nature (Fig. 13). The tradition that Bodhisattva Nāgārjuna lived in a cave c. 3 km east of the Ramtek may have also aroused Buddhist interest (Hiriāl 1908, p. 204, pp. 206-208). The name of the organisation testifies to this tradition. Real historical evidence for Buddhist activity in the neighbourhood is provided by three Buddhist bronzes found in Hamlapuri, 5 km to the East (Jamkhedkar 1985).
- 33 After the conference A.M. Shastri wrote to me in a letter dated 13.10.99: "In the meantime I had an opportunity to examine the Mansar sealings in original as Shri A.K. Sharma wanted me to give my readings. I am happy to inform you that all of them are sealings (not seals) and give the names Pravareśvara and Jayavṛddhi, sometimes preceded by the honorific śrī and the former sometimes ends in genitive singular suffix *śya*."
- 34 EM 130. It has to be admitted, though, that these legends are not immediately clear from the "Age [Eye-?] copy of the inscribed sealing" published in Fig. 1 (EM 130). Two impressions (sealings) are redrawn in this Figure; in one of them I can read: *pravara* = = ; in the other: *pravara* = = . The reported reading *jaiavṛddhi* may be a corruption of the reading *jayaavṛddhi* as reported by A.M. Shastri.
- 35 Cf. the size of the bricks found in the excavation of the Vākāṭaka site in Mandhal. IAR 1975-76, p. 36 reports about BHK-I that "the bricks used were of two sizes, viz. 44x23x8 cm and 40x24x8 cm". Cf. Shastri 1977-78, p. 145 who reports that the size of the bricks of site MDL-II is 44x23x8 cm.
- 36 A.M. Shastri wrote to me in a letter dated 24.4.2001: "Sharmaji brought to me two blocks of stone bearing fragmentary inscriptions: one of them in late Vākāṭaka box-headed characters and the other in slightly earlier nail-headed characters. The letters on the latter were almost worn out while those on the first were so far as preserved absolutely clear and I gave him my reading."
- 37 EM 130 mentions "a base of an earthen jar having eleven holes on fine slipped red ware."
- 38 The account would have gained in plausibility, if parallel sites in India would have been discussed that likewise show a continuous alternation of Hindu temples and Buddhist stūpas (along with the additional peculiarity that only Hindu images have been preserved).
- 39 I have not come across a reference to an altar in the form of a turtle. See above p. 19.
- 40 IAR 1953-54, 10f. Ramachandran 1951-52, pp. 28-31.
- 41 Sharma 1960, p. 118.
- 42 Sharma 1960, p. 118.
- 43 Sharma 1960, p. 122f. See Plates 33, 43 No. 38.
- 44 Sharma 1960, p. 125. See Plates 36-38.
- 45 Sharma 1960, p. 126.
- 46 Von Schlingloff 1968-69, p. 188: "Die tatsächliche Erklärung für die zwischen die Ziegel gelegten Knochen ist überhaupt nicht im Ritual der Feuerschichtung zu suchen, sondern liegt in einem ganz anderen Bereich. Es gibt nur einen Ritus, der das Einlegen von Gebeinen zwischen Ziegel erforderlich macht, und dies ist die Schichtung einer Grabstätte (*śmaśāna*). Nach der Leichenverbrennung werden die Gebeine eines Verstorbenen zuerst in einer Urne beigesetzt; zu einem späteren Zeitpunkt sind sie aus der Urne herauszunehmen und - falls der Verstorbene zu Lebzeiten eine Feuerstätte geschichtet hat - in einer Grabstätte niederzulegen, die in der Art einer Feuerstätte angelegt werden soll."
- 47 Thapar in Agni II, p. 27.
- 48 Wellsted 1934, p. 164 reports the finding of a "small snake image of greenish soapstone and some pottery" in a brick (burial?) shaft c. 1.5 km to the east of the Hiḍimbā Tekḍī, which are kept in the British Museum (Reg. No. 1930.10.7.1-25).
- 49 Though not mentioned in the report, some bones were recovered from one of the two natural caves in the rock at the northern side of the hill during my stay at the site. In the report these caves are identified as a "shrine" and "meditation chamber" (EM 129).
- 50 Ray 1960, p. 311. See also Bodewitz 1977-78.
- 51 Gonda 1980, p. 154.
- 52 *Bṛhatsaṃhitā* 53.2-3: *kim api kila bhūtam abhavad rundhānam rodasi śarireṇa | tad amarāganena sahasā viniḡrhyādhomukhaṃ nyastam || 2 || yatra ca yena gr̥hitaṃ vibudhenādhiṣṭhitāḥ sa tatraiva | tadamaramayaṃ*

- vidhātā vāstunaram kalpayāmāsa* || 3 ||.
- 53 N.R. Bhatt, dealing with Āgamas and Silpa, notes: 'The performer of the installation ceremony then draws a diagram called Vāstumaṇḍala on the site made even and clean and performs a fire ritual to please the deities of the lords of this maṇḍala. Vāstu means a site for dwelling. Vāstupuruṣa is a deity who governs the site and is lying on the site, and his limbs are occupied by different deities. Before construction, these deities are to be pleased and permission to use the site is to be obtained. This ritual is named *vāstpūpujā*' (Bhatt 1984, 15).
- 54 IAR 1983-84, p. 58. In the neighbourhood of this site a few sculptural fragments, which the excavators identify as 'Kṣetrapāla Bhairava,' were found earlier. If complete it would have measured c.17m. On account of stone inscriptions found in Kandhar of the time of the Rāṣṭrakuṭa king Kṛṣṇa III (A.D. 939-65), the excavators identify the shrine unearthed as that of the Kṣetrapāla. I am much obliged to Frans Janssen who drew my attention to this excavation.
- 55 The longitudinal axis of the Mansar clay figure runs from north-west to south-east rather than from west to east.
- 56 According to Joshi and Sharma this image was found "near the south-western end of the [Vākāṭaka] temple" (EM 129).
- 57 The excavators ascribe the first phase of this temple to Pravarasena I or his son Rudrasena I (c. A.D. 275 - 360). In absence of a detailed stratigraphic account this hypothesis can neither be proven nor disproven. If it would turn out to be correct, the thesis advanced by A.M. Shastri and accepted by me, to the effect that the homeland of the Vākāṭakas in the third and first half of the fourth century was in Bundelkhand, has to be reconsidered. In the inscriptions of his successors king Pravarasena I (c. A.D. 275-335), called *samrāt*, is said to have performed several Vedic sacrifices: six ectypes of the Jyotiṣṭoma, viz. the Agniṣṭoma, Āptoryāma, Ukthya, Ṣoḍaśin, Atirātra, Vājapeya (including the Brhaspatisava), next to the Sādyaskra and four Aśvamedha sacrifices. For all these soma sacrifices the fire-altar constructed in the Agnicayana is the most prestigious. Balancing all our evidence of the early Vākāṭakas, however, it appears as yet more plausible to assume that Pravareśvara II at the beginning of his rule, while still residing in Nandivardhana, built this temple named after himself (Pravareśvara, see above p. 4) and later, when his residence had moved to the foot of the hill, rebuilt or enlarged this temple to a state sanctuary from where official charters were issued (*vaijayikadharmasthāna*, called "Pravareśvaradevakulasthāna"; see above p. 4).
- 58 Identified with the hamlet Tewar, c. 10 km south-west of Jabalpur City. Mirashi 1982, 66f., p. 72 l. 1: *tripurivāsakā* (t).
- 59 Mirashi 1982, p. 70 f.; cf. Mirashi in JESI (1980), 86 ff. The interpretation of this verse is controversial. Fleet in CII III (1888), 53-54, ll. 10-11 reads: *samuditaba(la)kośān pu(ṣya)mitrāmś ca (j)itvā*; he takes this as a reference to the tribe of the Puṣyamitras. Fleet admitted in a note that the second syllable of the name was damaged. Mirashi 1982 (IRP I, 70), following a pro-proposal of Divekar, conjectures the reading: *samuditaba(la)kośān yuddhy a)mitrāmś ca (j)sitvā*; that is, 'after having vanquished in battle (*yudhi*) his enemies whose wealth and power had increased,' a reading accepted in the revised edition (1981) of CII III (p. 315 vs. 4).
- 60 Mirashi 1982 (= IRP I), p. 70.
- 61 There is ample evidence that Vidiśā was Rāmagupta's stronghold, see EI XXXVIII, pp. 46-49; cf. Mirashi 1982, pp. 56-64; Joshi 1992, p. 121. Though less well attested, a similar struggle may also have taken place after the death of Candragupta II, when Kumāragupta had to address the challenge of his elder (?) brother Govindagupta (EI XXVII, pp. 12-18; Thaplyal 1972, pp. 66, 96).
- 62 Bhandarkar's translation (CII III, pp. 299, 302) of: (*na*)rapati-(bh)ujagānām mānadarpotphaṇānām pratikṛti(ga)rudājñā(m) nirviṣi(m) cāvakartā || 2 ||. The Sanskrit (and translation) is problematic; one would expect something like 'ājñayā nirviṣikartā. I agree with Bhandarkar (in CII III, p. 302 n. 3) that this simile probably alludes to the Nāgas, but unlike him (CII III, p. 81), I assume that they were Ghaṭotkaca's allies rather than his adversaries.
- 63 Kevala-Narasimha Temple Inscription (Bakker 1997, p. 165) vs. 17 (l. 9).
- 64 The upheaval in the western part of the Gupta kingdom is also apparent from the fact that from the time of Kumāragupta's death the issuing of charters by the Gupta feudatories ruling in Vālkhā (Anūpa), south of Malwa, is disrupted; these rulers had in their many inscriptions, which are dated in the Gupta era, referred to the grace of the *paramabhaṭṭāraka* (Ramesh & Tewari 1990, p. viii). About this time, or shortly afterwards, this region came under the sway of Vatsagulma (Bakker 1997, 39).
- 65 Bhitari Stone Pillar Inscription of Skandagupta (CII III, 315 ll. pp. 12-14) vs. 6: *pitari divam upe(ṭe) viplutām (va)ñśalaksīmīm, bhujabalavijitārir yah pratiṣṭhā(pya) bhū yah() jitam iti paritoṣān (m)ātaram sāsraneṭrām, hataripur iva (kr)ṣṇo devakim abhyu(peta)ḥ* (|| 6* ||).
- 66 ĀSS 16.22.3: *brahma jajñānam iti puṣkaraparna upariṣṭān nirbādham rukman upadhāya hiraṇyagarbhaḥ sam avartatāgra iti tasmīn hiraṇmayam puruṣam prācīnam uttānam dakṣiṇenātṛṇam prānī mukha upadhāya puruṣasāma gāyeti sampreṣyati* || 3 ||. Cf. ŚBr 7.4.1.7-21 and the *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* (5.2.7.2) in the translation of Keith: "He puts down a gold disk; gold is immortality; verily in immortality he piles the fire, for propagation. He puts a golden man, to support the world of the sacrificer; if he were to put it over the perforation in the brick, he would obstruct the breath of cattle and of the sacrificer; he puts it down on the south side with head to the east: he supports the world of the sacrificer; he does not obstruct the breath of cattle and the sacrificer."
- 67 TaiS 4.2.8.f (transl. Keith): "The drop hath fallen on the earth, the sky, on this seat, and on the one which was aforetime; the drop that wandereth over the third seat I offer in the seven Hotrās."
- 68 TaiS 4.2.8.g-i (transl. Keith): "Homage to the serpents which are on the earth, the serpents in the atmosphere, in the sky, to those serpents homage [. . .]" etc. Cf. *Vārāha Śrautasūtra* 2.1.6.16. *Baudhāyana Śrautasūtra* misses this element.
- 69 ĀSS 16.22.4: *drapsas caskandeti puruṣam abhimṛśya namo astu sarpebhya iti tisṛbhir abhimantrya kṛṇuṣva pāja iti pañcabhir uttaravedivat puruṣam vyāghārya sruvāc upadadhātīty uktam* || 4 ||.
- 70 According to the tradition of the Vājasaneyins it is placed on the mortar (see ŚBr 7.5.1.26).
- 71 ĀSS 16.27.22: *namo astu sarpebhya iti dakṣiṇe 'mse sarpaśira upadadhāyā viṣūcīnam paśuśīrśaiḥ*. The verb *upadhā* is used for piling bricks as well as for the installation/placing of other items. It is therefore not clear whether a representation in brick (*citi*) or a real snake head is intended here. Tsuji 1983, p. 156 takes *Mānavasrautasūtra* 8.3 to mean "piling of a serpent head". *Baudhāyana* speaks of a "real" snake head (BSS 10.9, Agni II, p. 499) that should be placed on the right (southern) part of the forehead. It may be directed towards the direction from which danger threatens

- the country (BSS 10.30; Agni II, p. 539).
- 72 The Puruṣa Hymn, TaiĀr 3.12 (= RV X.90). As has been observed by Caland, this element may have been derived from the tradition of the Maitrāyaṇīyas (*Maitrāyaṇī Saṃhitā* 3.5.1), as it is not found in the *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* nor in *Baudhāyana Śrautasūtra*. The *Śrautasūtra* of the Maitrāyaṇīyas, the *Mānava Śrautasūtra*, indeed reads as follows (6.1.8.1, 3): 'He should construct the 'man-layer' (*puruṣaciti*) on the northern shoulder (*uttarasminn aṃṣe*). [the same formulas] Aloof from the upper part of the body (*uttarārḥāt*) he should construct the head of the snake (*sarpaśiras*) turned away (from the body) by means of the "Homage to the serpents" verses (*sarpanāma*); or he should assign it (only) and not (actually) construct it.' (The same alternative in ĀSS 16.27.23).
- 73 The *Hiranyakeśi Śrautasūtra* places the serpent head on the left shoulder (see Caland ad ĀSS 16.27.22). As to the place of the human figure Caland (ad loc.) remarks: "Art und Weise ihrer Schichtung sind undeutlich".
- 74 It is conceivable that the theologians of the White Yajurveda, the Vājasaneyins (as well as Baudhāyana), in view of their identification of the altar with the Puruṣa (SBr 6.1.1.3-7), took the totality of the bricks of the first layer itself as a representation of the *puruṣa*, which would render another *puruṣa* figure, in addition of the man of gold and the altar itself, redundant. On the other hand, though, the omission of the serpent head remains intriguing. As we have seen, the serpents were earlier invoked, by the same verses but without the exemplifying head, after the man of gold had been installed and the Puruṣasāman had been sung.
- 75 ĀSS 16.6.2-3; cf. VSS 2.1.1.50 and MSS 6.1.2.23 (*vaiśya* and *rājanyabandhu*). According to *Baudhāyana Śrautasūtra* 10.9 it should be the head of a vaiśya killed in battle (Agni II, p. 499).
- 76 *mṛdā pralipya nidadhāti*, ĀSS 16.6.7; cf. BSS 10.10 (Agni II, p. 501). The ritual according to Caland's translation of Āpastamba is as follows: "Dann geht er mit sieben oder einundzwanzig Bohnen in der Hand, um einen Menschenkopf zu holen, der von einem Vaiśya oder Kṣatriya herrührt, welcher durch einen Pfeil (im Kriege) oder durch den Blitz getötet worden ist. Nach-dem er die Bohnen in der Nähe (des Körpers) hingeworfen hat, haut er den Menschenkopf ab mit der Formel: "Der du hier bist, dem dir dieses Haupt angehört, durch dieses Haupt sollst du dort im Besitze eines Hauptes sein" und legt dann an die Stelle des Kopfes einen siebenfach durchlöchernten Ameisenhaufen nieder. Er singt, während er rechts um das Haupt herumgeht, die drei an Yama gerichteten Verse [...] (ĀSS 16.6.2-4).
- 77 KSS 16.1.14: *parivṛte puruṣasamjñapanam*.
- 78 KSS 16.1.32: *anyāni vā hiraṇmayāni vā mṛnmayāni vānālabhyaitān*. Cf. *Dvaidha Sūtra* (BSS 22.2): "As for the preparation of the heads of the sacrificial victims: Baudhāyana says they should be either real or made of clay. Śāliki says that they should be real ones only. Aupamanyava says that they should be made of gold" (Agni II, p. 613).
- 79 KSS 16.1.19-20: *caturṇām apsu kāyaprāsanam* || 19 || *tato mṛd iṣṭakāṛthāpaś ca* || 20 ||; cf. ĀSS 16.8.1.
- 80 SBr 6.2.1.7. Cf. *Karmānta Sūtra* (BSS 25.29) which refers to this practice (Agni II, p. 653f.).
- 81 *śriyaḥ*, identified with the elixir of life (*rasa*) in SBr 6.1.1.4.
- 82 SBr 6.2.1.11.
- 83 TaiS 5.4.11. See BSS 17.28 (Agni II, pp. 666-675).

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